

Do Green Marketing Strategies Influence Green Buying Intentions? Evidence from Developing Economy

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Abstract:- This study aims to investigate the influence of green marketing strategies on the green buying intentions of Bangladeshi green consumers. A convenience sample of 277 consumers was used. The study employed structural equation modeling to scrutinize the impact of green marketing strategies. The results indicate that all the green variables (value, packaging, labeling, price place, and promotion) significantly impact green buying intentions. The green promotion has the highest impact and the green place has the lowest impact on the green buying intentions of consumers. Marketers and experts may take necessary steps for the betterment of business marketing as well as for a sustainable environment and livelihood.

Keywords:- green strategy, green buying intention; green consumer behavior; green marketing, Bangladesh.

I. INTRODUCTION

An environment surrounds us, and this environment is being negatively affected by human activities (Vani, 2022). Every government worldwide is trying to reduce its influence on the environment (Vani, 2022). Nowadays, people are more concerned with the environment than before (Vani, 2022). Due to the new concern of society, marketers have started to modify their business activities and integrate environmental aspects into business activities (Vani, 2022). Green issues have been incorporated into various literature by academic disciplines, for example, marketing (Kaur et al., 2022; Vani, 2022), human resource management (Chowdhury et al., 2019; Tanova & Bayighomog, 2022), education (Zhong et al., 2022). "Green Marketing" is included in the syllabus, and along with marketing, students study green marketing (Vani, 2022). Green marketing develops and sells goods and services which are environmentally friendly. Green marketing incorporates marketing strategies in a way that considers society's long-term interests and is connected to the companies, consumers, and environment (Karnai et al., 2021). Green marketing considers sustainable designs, tools and environmentally friendly strategies to fulfil consumers' needs (Chowdhury & Roy, 2015; Mohammed, 2021; Machova et al., 2022). Marketing should not be defined as only sales and advertisements; a wide range of activities are included in it, for example, product ideation, distribution, packaging, transportation, promotion, pricing, etc. (Saleem et al., 2021). Green marketing includes a wide range of environment-oriented marketing activities, for example,

green design, production, integrated marketing communication, etc. (Saleem et al., 2021).

For a few years, the environment has been facing several challenges, such as global warming, air pollution, water pollution, climate change, etc., which have led consumers to be more aware of the consequences of these challenges (Govender and Govender, 2016). These challenges have prioritized the business atmosphere and public thinking (Govender and Govender, 2016). Once, quality of life, sustainability, society's well-being, the cohesion of society, and transmission of values were just in morality, but nowadays, these are the norms in business ethics for the sake of the society, environment, and organization (Murin et al., 2015; Islam et al., 2021). By applying green marketing, marketers can bring betterment for our planet and inspire the public who are conscious of the consequence of the challenges the environment is facing today. Again, by giving importance to sustainable green products, companies can decrease damage to our environment. That's why green marketing is also called eco-marketing or environmental marketing (Machova et al., 2022). Green marketing makes the marketer capable of occupying a distinctive position in the consumers' mindset, increasing the number of loyal customers. As a result, the marketer gets a higher competitive advantage in the marketplace. Marketers who adopt green marketing strategies can minimize the negative impact of manufacturing on the environment. They can manufacture recyclable products, decrease the consumption of energy, decrease the utilization of natural resources, increase credibility, accomplish innovation, confirm longitudinal growth and earn higher revenue.

There are several pieces of research where the researchers have narrated the influence of green marketing strategies on purchasing intention and consumer behavior in several nations (Hossain and Rahman, 2018; Kaur et al., 2022; Mehraj & Qureshi, 2020). Since Bangladesh is the eighth most populated country in the world, more research is needed on green marketing issues to protect the country's ecology from ecological hazards (Hossain and Rahman, 2018; Kaur et al., 2022). There is inadequate work on the effect of green marketing strategies adopted by marketers to satisfy green consumers in Bangladesh (Hossain and Rahman, 2018). Previous studies especially measure the impact of a green marketing mix on green consumer buying intentions (Hossain and Rahman, 2018; Kaur et al., 2022; Roy et al., 2021). The marketing mix variables were the

green product, green price, green place and green promotion. But the green product variable comprises three factors: green value, green packaging, and green labelling. Again, no work has been done to investigate the significant impact of green value, green packaging, and green labelling on green buying intentions in the context of Bangladesh. Therefore, this study has been designed to fill up the gap. This study aims to scrutinize the impact of green marketing strategy variables on consumers' buying intention in the context of Bangladesh.

A. Green Consumer

Green marketers are those who purchase green products (Vani, 2022). Green consumers' purpose is to save themselves the globe through their purchasing power (Zeynalova&Namazova, 2022). All purchasing activities of green consumers are based on the intention to ensure the ecological balance (Vani, 2022). By avoiding buying products that are detrimental to the environment, green consumers contribute greatly to the environment (Vani, 2022). Green consumers do not buy unwholesome products; detrimental to the environment during production, usage, and after usage; they do not consume more energy and elements that endanger different species (Vani, 2022). Therefore, a green consumer adopts environmentally friendly behaviours and purchases green products (Vani, 2022).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Green Value

Value is the difference between the benefits of preserving and consuming a product and the cost of obtaining that product. Green products meet consumer needs in a way that involves environmental well-being (Patterson and Spreng, 1997). Previous researchers proved that green value is an important element of green marketing strategies, which influences green consumers' buying intention. Therefore, marketers emphasize green value perception because it enhances consumer purchasing interest (Steenkamp and Geyskens, 2006). When consumers perceive increased value from a product, their purchasing intention increases for this product (Chang & Chen, 2008). Perceived green value and buying intention are highly correlated (Dhewi et al., 2018). Perceived value greatly influences increasing sales (Dhewi et al., 2018). So, the hypothesis is:

H1: Green value significantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

B. Green Packaging

Green packaging is served as the marketing strategy to contain, identify, explain, protect, visualize, communicate and make the green product marketable (Govender & Govender, 2016). Green packaging is designed and produced in such a way it is beneficial to the users, consumers, and manufacturers of packaged products (Kozik, 2020). In recent years, packaging has been designed and produced in terms of environmental aspects (Kozik, 2020). One of the main reasons for environmental pollution is the usage of plastic. Consumers are more environment-oriented

and avoid purchasing plastic-packaged products. Therefore, marketers should try not to sell plastic packaged products and emphasize recycled packaging because consumers' green purchasing decision is greatly influenced by green packaging (Agyeman, 2014). According to Davis (2014), female consumers prioritize packaging more than males. Hence, green packaging attracts and encourages green purchasing (Jerda&Sahayaselvi, 2018). So, the hypothesis is:

H2: Green packaging significantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

C. Green Labeling

Green labels are the symbols used to describe a product as environmentally safe, and the product is considered a green product (Sharma and Kushwaha 2019). Green labels are considered in terms of environmental standards (Sharma and Kushwaha 2019). Green label is considered an important medium of communication that conveys information to consumers and helps them to take purchasing decision (Rex and Baumann, 2007). Since green labeling is the appearance of an environment-friendly product, most consumers like green-labeled products compared to the traditional labeled product (Sharma and Kushwaha 2019). So, green labeling increases sales, and the hypothesis is:

H3: Green labeling significantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

D. Green Pricing

An individual has to pay an amount to obtain ownership of something; this amount is called a price (Burrow, 2008). Marketers should emphasize green pricing since it is one of the important elements of the green marketing mix (Govender & Govender, 2016). Price is the prime reason consumers do not purchase a green product because of its expense (Bukhari, 2011). However, consumers are frequently purchasing green products today (Ahmmed, 2012). Especially, the young generation is more interested in purchasing green products and paying a fixed amount (Anvar & Venter, 2014). Green products or services, recyclable paper, brand-new coffee strainer, and renewable energy facility creates the floor for green pricing (Ahmmed, 2012). Different costs incorporated because of the consideration of environmental standards are added to green products' production costs (Kaur et al., 2022). When consumers perceive that the consumed benefit exceeds the cost, they are willing to pay the price fixed by the marketer (Abzari et al., 2013). Therefore, green product prices significantly affect buying intention (Widayanti, 2020). Previous researches show that consumers of green product are not reluctant to pay a higher price for green products (Bathmathan&Rajadurai, 2019). Therefore, the hypothesis is:

H4: Green price significantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

E. Green Place

The place consists of the firms and people who make a product available to the consumers. The closer location and easy accessibility impact consumer buying decisions since most consumers are not interested in buying green products or services by travelling far (Kontic, 2010). Green products can be available for consumers in supermarkets (Gittell et al., 2015). Hence, marketers should give importance to the availability of green products in the nearest place to the consumer (Kaur et al., 2022). Therefore, the hypothesis is:

H5: Green place significantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

F. Green Promotion

Green promotion introduces a green product in the marketplace and persuades green consumers to purchase that product. When consumers are not knowledgeable enough about a product, visual presentation in the product's packaging is an important tool for marketing promotion (Govender & Govender, 2016). The green promotion also works to create consciousness of the hazards the

environment faces today and purchase eco-friendly goods that are biodegradable, produced with recycled materials, and CFC-free. Advertising effectively increases customers' knowledge about a product and its influence on the environment (Ansar, 2013). Nowadays, emotional advertising is the priority for marketers to influence the buying intention of consumers (Ahern, 2013). So, marketers can use environmental advertising to increase the motivation of consumers to purchase green products. (Govender & Govender, 2016). Previous studies show that green promotion has been able to modify green consumers' traditional purchasing habits, and the habits have been shifted to green products (Agus&Rasmen, 2019). If marketers implement these promotional strategies properly, consumers will be attracted to green products, increasing green purchasing. Therefore, the hypothesis is:

H6: Green promotion importantly influences consumers' green buying intentions.

The proposed hypothesized model is represented in figure 1.

Fig. 1: Hypothesized Research Model

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Data Collection

For collecting primary data, a personal interview technique was employed. Convenience sampling methods have been used for collecting information from customers who are well known for the term "green marketing". All the constructs from the literature were with standard scales. Since a structured questionnaire makes it easier to answer the questions, a well-structured questionnaire has been formulated by the researchers (Roy & Ahmed, 2016). For collecting the consumer responses, a five-point Likert scale was used. In this study, one presented "strongly disagree", and five presented "strongly agree". In the dimensions of green marketing strategies, researchers have used 22 statements for ratings of the performance. There were four

statements relating to the dependent variable, green buying intention. The items are given in appendix 1. A total of 300 respondents were given the questionnaire to fill up. After final checking, 277 questionnaire was suitable for further analysis. The analysis was performed by using SPSS and SmartPLS software.

B. Consumers demographic analysis

53.07% of the consumers were female, and the rest were male. Most consumers are 20-25 years (45.49%) and are graduates (39.71%). Furthermore, the majority of green consumers are students (37.54%). Only 8.30% of the respondents have an income of more than 50000 Bangladeshi taka, whereas less than 30000 Bangladeshi taka (46.21%) (See Table 1).

		Male	Female	Total
Age	20-25	52 (40%)	74 (50.34%)	126 (45.49%)
	26-30	28 (21.54%)	24 (16.33%)	52 (18.77%)
	31-35	47 (36.15%)	43 (29.25%)	90 (32.49%)
	36-40	3 (2.31%)	6 (4.08%)	9 (3.25%)
		130 (46.93%)	147 (53.07%)	277 (100%)
Education	Undergraduate	24 (18.46%)	62 (42.18%)	86 (31.05%)
	Graduate	40 (30.77%)	70 (47.62%)	110 (39.71%)
	Post-graduate	60 (46.15%)	11 (7.48%)	71 (25.63%)
	Doctorate	6 (4.62%)	4 (2.72%)	10 (3.61%)
		130 (46.93%)	147 (53.07%)	277 (100%)
Occupation	Student	42 (32.31%)	62 (42.18%)	104 (37.54%)
	Homemaker	1 (0.77%)	54 (36.73%)	55 (19.86%)
	Own business	22 (16.92%)	20 (13.61%)	42 (15.16%)
	Professional	65 (50%)	11 (7.48%)	76 (27.44%)
		130 (46.93%)	147 (53.07%)	277 (100%)
Monthly Income	Less than 30,000	48 (36.92%)	80 (54.42%)	128 (46.21%)
	30,000-50,000	66 (50.77%)	60 (40.82%)	126 (45.49%)
	More than 50,000	16 (12.31%)	7 (4.76%)	23 (8.30%)
		130 (46.93%)	147 (53.07%)	277 (100%)

Table 1: Demographic profile of the respondents

IV. RESULTS

A. Assessment of the measurement model

To assess the measurement model, researchers check the factor loadings (λ), Cronbach's alpha (α), composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2020; Roy, 2022). The result found that the λ values for all variables were substantial and greater than the indicated threshold value of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2020). See table 2 and figure 2. Furthermore, the findings of construct consistency using α

values varied from 0.743 to 0.877, which was greater than the 0.70 indicated by Nunnally and Bernstein (1994). The CR values of all latent constructs varied from 0.837 to 0.924, which was much higher than the tolerable limit of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2020). Furthermore, the AVE values were greater than the cutoff value of 0.50 (Hair et al., 2010) for all the constructs. Based on these fit indicators, it was ensured that the model had appropriate convergent validity.

Factor	Items	λ	α	CR	AVE
Green Value	GVAL1	0.725	0.828	0.879	0.593
	GVAL2	0.803			
	GVAL3	0.754			
	GVAL4	0.765			
	GVAL5	0.801			
Green Packaging	GPAC1	0.824	0.743	0.837	0.562
	GPAC2	0.706			
	GPAC3	0.715			
	GPAC4	0.749			
Green Labeling	GLAB1	0.848	0.777	0.870	0.691
	GLAB2	0.796			
	GLAB3	0.849			
Green Price	GPRI1	0.799	0.834	0.889	0.667
	GPRI2	0.877			
	GPRI3	0.733			
	GPRI4	0.850			
Green Place	GPLA1	0.921	0.877	0.924	0.802
	GPLA2	0.884			
	GPLA3	0.881			
Green Promotion	GPRO1	0.850	0.820	0.892	0.734
	GPRO2	0.866			
	GPRO3	0.853			
Green Buying Intention	GBIN1	0.876	0.861	0.905	0.705
	GBIN2	0.855			
	GBIN3	0.821			
	GBIN4	0.804			

Table 2: Convergent validity

Again, to measure the discriminant validity of the model, Fornell&Larcker's (1981) criteria and Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT) were employed. According toFornell and Larcker's criteria, the inter-correlation between the construct must be less than the square root of

the AVE values. The study results meet these conditions. Again, the HTMT ratio value needs to be less than the threshold of 0.85 (Kline, 2015). The outcomes of the work affirm the criteria. So, the discriminant validity has no issues. See Table 3.

Fornell and Larcker's criteria

	Green Value	Green Packaging	Green Labeling	Green Price	Green Place	Green Promotion	Green Buying Intention
Green Value	0.770						
Green Packaging	0.562	0.750					
Green Labeling	0.651	0.470	0.832				
Green Price	0.638	0.472	0.674	0.817			
Green Place	0.568	0.504	0.513	0.533	0.896		
Green Promotion	0.567	0.485	0.598	0.666	0.599	0.857	
Green Buying Intention	0.671	0.580	0.653	0.669	0.597	0.659	0.839

HTMT ratio

Green Value							
Green Packaging	0.710						
Green Labeling	0.814	0.610					
Green Price	0.760	0.578	0.840				
Green Place	0.666	0.606	0.620	0.621			
Green Promotion	0.678	0.598	0.739	0.786	0.698		
Green Buying Intention	0.780	0.705	0.791	0.766	0.678	0.768	

Note: Bold diagonal elements represent the square root of AVE values.

Table 3: Discriminant validity

Fig. 2: The results of the measurement model

B. Structural equation model (SEM)

The study then proceeds by examining the structural model's path coefficients, illustrated in table 4 and figure 03. As for hypothesis, H1, the green value has a significant impact on green buying intention ($\beta = 0.187$, t-value = 2.841, p-value < 0.01). The hypothesis was supported, which confirms that the green value significantly positively impacts green buying intention. The study outcomes were supported by earlier research (Chang & Chen, 2008; Dhewi et al., 2018). The result found that green packaging is a substantial predictor of green buying intention because $\beta = 0.165$, t-value = 2.904, and p-value < 0.01. So, hypothesis H2 was supported, and the result is consistent with Jerda & Sahayaselvi's (2018) research work. According to hypothesis H3, green labeling significantly impacts green

buying intention. The results support the hypothesis ($\beta = 0.163$, t-value = 2.846, p-value < 0.01). The outcome is analogous to the previous work (Rex and Baumann, 2007). Again, as stated by H4, the green price significantly impacts green buying intention. Hypothesis H4 is supported by the study results ($\beta = 0.173$, t-value = 2.493, p-value < 0.05) and is also similar to the work of Widayanti (2020). Similarly, green place significantly predicts green buying intention ($\beta = 0.118$, t-value = 2.467, p-value < 0.05) and supports the hypothesis H5. The result is identical to Kaur et al.'s result (2022). Finally, green promotion is also an important predictor of green buying intention. The study results supported the proposition H6 ($\beta = 0.190$, t-value = 3.154, p-value < 0.01) and consistent with the earlier research work (Ahern, 2013; Agus & Rasmien, 2019).

Fig. 3: The results of the structural model

H	Relationships	β	t-values	p-values	Supported
H1	Green Value -> Green Buying Intention	0.187	2.841	0.005	Yes
H2	Green Packaging -> Green Buying Intention	0.165	2.904	0.004	Yes
H3	Green Labeling -> Green Buying Intention	0.163	2.846	0.004	Yes
H4	Green Price -> Green Buying Intention	0.173	2.493	0.013	Yes
H5	Green Place -> Green Buying Intention	0.118	2.467	0.014	Yes
H6	Green Promotion -> Green Buying Intention	0.190	3.154	0.002	Yes

Table 4: Structural Equation Model (SEM) with Results

C. Predictive power (R^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2)

The quality of the structural model was evaluated by the coefficient of determination (R^2) and predictive relevance (Q^2). The model has substantial explanatory power as green value, packaging, labeling, price, place, and promotion explain 63.9% of the variance in brand trust. Again, the predictive relevance value was .435, which is greater than 0, indicating good predictive relevance (Chin et al., 2020). The researchers also checked the goodness of fit (GoF) index. The approximate fit of the structural model was assessed by standardized root mean square residuals (SRMR) (Henseler, 2012). For a good fit of a model, the SRMR value should be less than 0.08 (Henseler, 2012). The SRMR value of the study was 0.067, which indicates considerable goodness of fit.

V. DISCUSSION

This research has been conducted for the purpose of describing the influence of green marketing mix essentials on the buying intention of the green consumer of Bangladesh after the pandemic period of Covid-19. Hence, it is a must for the producer and marketer to perceive the relevancy of the strategies of the marketing mix for attracting the green consumer towards green products produced and sold. The researchers have perceived that all the elements of green marketing considered by the commercial organization positively impact the purchasing decision of Bangladeshi green consumers towards pro-environmental products. The findings show that Bangladeshi consumers' purchasing intention is significantly impacted by green value, packaging, labelling, price, place, and

promotion. This way, it can be narrated that a green product is eco-friendly. A green product's quality is high, it is beneficial to health, and the cost of a green product is justified. So, most of the respondents perceive that the benefit of the green product outweighs the cost, and the perceived value significantly influence consumers' buying decision. Secondly, the aesthetic design or patterns motivates consumers' buying action. Green packaging is considered a means of pride and possession by green consumers. Some consumers do not observe the production and expiry date. Some are very concerned about labeling green products, which influences their purchasing intentions. The green product's price is reasonable to the consumers. The price of the green product is proportionate with its quality and other green aspects. Green products consumers want green products easily accessible in the green retail store. Green consumers know about the environmental benefits of green products through different promotional mixes that make them easily acceptable.

It is also emphasized that green places/channels had the lowest, and green promotion had the greatest influence on green purchasing intention. This states that Bangladeshi customers are encouraged by the green marketing offerings of the seller and convert their green purchasing intention into actual purchasing. It is also highlighted that the green consumers' trust in the offerings of the green seller is more important than the perception of the green product as the solution to environmental hazards. On the other hand, previous research proved that green product is the most significant factor influencing on green purchasing intention of Bangladeshi customers (Hossain & Rahman, 2018). In contrast, green products have less significance on the purchasing intention of Indian customers (Kaur et al., 2022).

VI. THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL IMPLICATION

By this exploratory research, the green marketing mix strategies have been affirmed as the significant predictors of green purchasing decisions of the consumers of Bangladesh, which will vitally contribute to the literature. Hence, policymakers and marketers should design marketing tools and tactics to incorporate the customer's positive ecological attitude into purchasing intention for green goods or services. To convert the buying decision of the green consumer into the green buying decision, a marketer should dominate the environmental emotions of the consumer. Ecology-sensitive customers are mainly involved in the move. In addition, emerging countries' consumers like Bangladesh are likely to be nature-oriented; hence, this nature orientation can be considered the floor by marketers to plan their future movements strategically.

The researchers experimented with the effect of green marketing mix elements on the green buying decisions of the people of Bangladesh for personal care products from a green perspective. There is a scarcity of literature perceiving the deepness of describing consumers' purchasing intentions in developing countries like Bangladesh. This research will contribute to the sense hub of green customers purchasing intentions. The adoption of green marketing mixes (green value, green packaging, green labeling, green price, green

place, and green promotion) will empirically accomplish the purchasing intention of Bangladeshi people. This study has contributed to the literature by suggesting a structural equation model with necessary constructs to reveal the green buying decision of the green consumers of Bangladesh. The finding of exploratory research plays a significant role in building up the theory around green marketing elements and consumers' intentions. Bangladeshi consumers' purchasing intentions are significantly influenced by green value, green packaging, green labeling, green price, green place and green promotion. Hence, the researchers suggest this study will encourage the marketers of green products to apply oppressive strategies related to green value, green packaging, green labeling, green price, green place and green promotion mixes. So, it is high time to design a new marketing campaign involving a consumer's necessity to consume a green product and contribute to saving the earth from further downfall.

VII. CONCLUSIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There is an increased demand for green products from the emergence of environmental protection, safety and health of families. More experiments are needed to justify the theoretical components that reveal the deepness of the categorical greenness of customers' purchasing intentions. Environmental attitude is a concept which is growing rapidly with consumer buying intention habits in Bangladesh. On the contrary, the upcoming scope of the research related to the 4Ps of marketing can require more and various measures, e. g., the 7Ps (product, price, place, promotion, packaging, positioning and people) of the green marketing strategies in Bangladesh. In the case of maintaining a greener and cleaner environment, buyers are not reluctant to pay more for green promotions. So, green advertising play's vital role in agricultural countries like India for buying intentions. The organizations that are improving with creative objects, resources and newness, saving the ecology and describing the task assimilate the conclusions will get the maximum benefits in future.

This study cannot overcome four limitations: Firstly, a cross-sectional design has been used, determining the practical value of the findings for the producers and marketers. Secondly, this exploratory analysis does not generalize Western and developed nations since this study has been conducted in an economy that assimilates unique cultural characteristics completely different from developed nations. Thirdly, random sampling may be used since the present study only uses a convenience sampling technique. Fourthly, the researchers have shown only direct relation; future research may use mediator variables, i. e. environmental attitude and green trust. This research is limited to the emerging nation in the time frame post-pandemic (Bangladesh). This study shows the path for further research to use this empirical model in other emerging countries with diversified geographical locations and different settings. Moreover, if similar studies are conducted in a longitudinal setting, these can increase the pro-environmental measures for sustainable consumption.

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Appendix 1

Constructs	Statements	Source
Green Value (GVAL)	GVAL1: The product's environmental performance meets my expectation.	Kanade & Harwani, 2022
	GVAL2: Green products are good for health.	
	GVAL3: This product's environmental functions provide very good value for me.	
	GVAL4: Purchase this product because it has more conservation.	
	GVAL5: I order this product because it is ecologically friendly.	
Green Packaging (GPAC)	GPAC1: The packaging is made from recyclable materials.	Kanade & Harwani, 2022
	GPAC2: The packaging is biodegradable.	
	GPAC3: The packaging is recyclable and reusable.	
	GPAC4: The product has no excessive packaging.	
Green Labeling (GLAB)	GLAB1: Green advertisements are continuously trustworthy.	Kanade & Harwani, 2022
	GLAB2: I contemplate what is printed on eco-labels, to be precise.	
	GLAB3: The information on eco-label is habitually easy to realize.	
Green price (GPRI)	GPRI1: The ecological benefits justify the price of green products.	Kaur et al., 2022
	GPRI2: Green product prices should be reasonable to motivate consumers to buy.	
	GPRI3: The price and quality of green products are proportionate.	
	GPRI4: The enhanced performance of green products justifies their price.	
Green Place (GPLA)	GPLA1: Green products are regularly available nearby.	Kaur et al., 2022
	GPLA2: Green products are readily available nearby.	
	GPLA3: Green products are widely available in all places.	
Green Promotion (GPRO)	GPRO1: I tend to pay attention to advertisement messages about the environment.	Kaur et al., 2022
	GPRO2: Consumers are facilitated by environmental messages to make an informed purchasing decision.	
	GPRO3: Green advertisements increase consumers' awareness of the benefits of green products.	
Green Buying Intention (GBIN)	GBIN1: I am willing to pay more for a green product, avoiding cheaper ones that harm the environment.	Kaur et al., 2022
	GBIN2: I will consider buying green products as they conserve energy resources.	
	GBIN3: I will consider buying green products as they are recycled materials.	
	GBIN4: I have the perception that green products have more excellent added value, and therefore I am willing to pay more.	